

TEACHING STRATEGIES AND PROBLEMS OF TECHNOLOGY-VOCATIONAL-LIVELIHOOD (TVL) TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

Technology-Vocational-Livelihood (TVL) education plays a vital role in preparing senior high school learners with practical skills and competencies necessary for employment, entrepreneurship, and lifelong learning. This study assessed the teaching strategies employed by TVL teachers in Mangga High School, Candaba, Pampanga during the School Year 2024–2025. Specifically, it examined the extent of practice of teaching strategies along entrepreneurial, contextualized, experiential, constructivist, and authentic approaches, as well as the problems encountered by teachers in the implementation of the TVL program. The study utilized a quantitative–descriptive research design with TVL teachers as respondents. Data were collected through a researcher-constructed questionnaire and analyzed using the weighted mean. Findings revealed that the teaching strategies were highly practiced, with an overall weighted mean of 4.28. Among the strategies, entrepreneurial teaching strategy ranked first, followed by experiential, authentic, contextualized, and constructivist teaching strategies. The study also identified several serious problems encountered by teachers, particularly inadequate facilities and equipment, inadequate teacher training and competency, lack of instructional materials, increased workloads, student engagement and learning styles, and curriculum alignment and assessment. These challenges affect the effective implementation of TVL instruction and the development of students' technical skills. Based on the findings, intervention measures were proposed to address the identified concerns and enhance the effectiveness of TVL teaching. The study highlights the importance of providing adequate resources, continuous teacher training, and institutional support to strengthen the implementation of the TVL program and improve the quality of technical-vocational education.

Keywords: *Technology-Vocational-Livelihood education, teaching strategies, TVL teachers, senior high school, technical-vocational education, instructional challenges*

INTRODUCTION

Quality education is widely recognized as a fundamental driver of national development and social transformation. Globally, education systems are expected to equip learners with competencies that enable them to respond to economic, technological, and social changes. The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) emphasizes that education is a critical foundation for sustainable development and inclusive growth. In line with this vision, Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4) seeks to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all by 2030 (UNESCO, 2016). This global commitment highlights the need for education systems to provide learners with relevant knowledge, skills, and values that prepare them to actively participate in the workforce and contribute to nation-building.

In the Philippine context, the integration of technical and vocational education into the basic education curriculum has become a strategic response to the demands of the modern labor market. The Technology and Vocational Livelihood (TVL) track under the K to 12 curriculum aims to equip senior high school learners with industry-relevant competencies that enhance employability and entrepreneurial capability. Through hands-on learning experiences, practical training, and industry immersion, the TVL program provides learners with opportunities to develop skills aligned with workforce demands (Department of Education, 2019; Okabe, 2018). As such, TVL education serves as a pathway for students who intend to pursue employment, entrepreneurship, or further technical specialization.

The TVL track covers diverse areas including Home Economics, Information and Communication Technology, Industrial Arts, and Agri-Fishery Arts. These learning areas emphasize the acquisition of practical competencies, work values, and life skills essential for productivity and employability. The curriculum is closely aligned with the standards of the Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA), which provides national certification for specific competencies. These certifications allow graduates to demonstrate verified technical skills that are recognized locally and internationally, thereby increasing their opportunities in the labor market (TESDA, 2020; Barcelona et al., 2023).

Despite the promising goals of TVL education, its effective implementation largely depends on the competency and preparedness of teachers. Teachers serve as the primary facilitators of learning who translate curriculum objectives into meaningful classroom experiences. Research indicates that teacher competence, teaching strategies, and access to instructional resources significantly influence the success of technical-vocational programs (Calanog, 2021; Abella et al., 2021). When teachers are equipped with adequate training, industry exposure, and pedagogical skills, they are

better able to guide students in acquiring practical competencies and work values necessary for the real world.

However, several challenges continue to affect the delivery of TVL education in many schools. Among these are limited instructional facilities, inadequate equipment, lack of specialized training, and teachers being assigned to teach subjects outside their field of expertise. These challenges may hinder the effective acquisition of competencies among learners and affect overall learning outcomes (Tingzon & Buyok, 2022; Bawar, 2019). Furthermore, the selection of appropriate teaching strategies plays a crucial role in ensuring that students remain motivated and actively engaged in skill-based learning activities that characterize TVL instruction.

The present study is grounded in the educational philosophy of experiential learning proposed by John Dewey, particularly his theory of self-activity and “learning by doing.” Dewey emphasized that meaningful learning occurs when learners actively engage in real-life experiences that allow them to construct knowledge through interaction and problem solving. In technical-vocational education, this philosophy is particularly relevant because learners develop competencies through hands-on activities, simulations, and authentic tasks that mirror real workplace situations (Kolb, 2017; Flinders & Thornton, 2021). Such learner-centered approaches encourage creativity, collaboration, and practical skill development.

Recognizing the importance of TVL education and the challenges associated with its implementation, this study aims to examine the extent of teaching strategies practiced by TVL teachers and identify the problems they encounter in the teaching-learning process. Specifically, the study focuses on entrepreneurial, contextualized, experiential, constructivist, and authentic teaching strategies used by teachers in senior high school. The findings of the study will serve as a basis for proposing intervention measures that may enhance instructional practices and address existing challenges, thereby improving the quality and effectiveness of TVL education for senior high school learners.

Research Questions

This study assessed the teaching strategies of the Senior High School Technology-Vocational-Livelihood (TVL) teachers in Mangga High School, Candaba, Pampanga during the school year 2024-2025. Specifically, it sought to answer the following sub-problems:

1. What is the extent of practice of the TVL teachers along the following teaching strategies:
 - 1.1. Entrepreneurial;
 - 1.2. Contextualized;
 - 1.3. Experiential;
 - 1.4. Constructivist; and
 - 1.5. Authentic teaching strategies?

2. What are the problems being encountered by the teachers in teaching TVL and how serious are they?
3. What intervention measures can be proposed to address the problems being encountered by the TVL teachers?

Basic Assumptions

This study was premised on the following basic assumptions:

1. The senior high school TVL teachers moderately practiced the different teaching strategies.
2. The senior high school teachers encounter very serious problems in teaching TVL.
3. The proposed intervention measures can address the problems being encountered by the TVL teachers.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a quantitative–descriptive research design to assess the teaching strategies of Senior High School Technology-Vocational-Livelihood (TVL) teachers in Mangga High School, Candaba, Pampanga during the School Year 2024–2025. The quantitative–descriptive approach was deemed appropriate because it allows the researcher to systematically describe and analyze existing conditions without manipulating variables. Specifically, the study examined the extent to which TVL teachers practice various teaching strategies, namely entrepreneurial, contextualized, experiential, constructivist, and authentic strategies. In addition, the design enabled the researcher to determine the problems encountered by teachers in teaching TVL and evaluate the level of seriousness of these problems.

The sources of data for this study were the Technology-Vocational-Livelihood (TVL) teachers of Mangga High School. These respondents were selected because they are directly involved in the delivery of TVL instruction and possess relevant experiences regarding the teaching strategies used in the classroom. Their responses provided the primary data necessary to answer the research questions concerning the extent of practice of teaching strategies and the challenges encountered in the implementation of TVL instruction.

A researcher-constructed questionnaire served as the primary instrument for data collection. The questionnaire consisted of two main parts. Part I determined the extent of practice of teaching strategies used by TVL teachers, focusing on entrepreneurial, contextualized, experiential, constructivist, and authentic teaching approaches. Part II identified the problems encountered by teachers in teaching TVL and assessed the degree of seriousness of these challenges. Prior to its administration, the instrument was presented to the research adviser for validation, and the recommended revisions were incorporated to enhance its clarity and relevance. The researcher personally distributed

and retrieved the questionnaires to ensure a higher response rate and accuracy in data gathering.

The weighted mean was used as the statistical tool to analyze and interpret the data collected. This statistical measure determined the average responses of the participants regarding the extent of teaching strategy practices and the seriousness of the problems encountered. The formula used was $WM = \frac{\sum fx}{N}$, where WM represents the weighted mean, $\sum fx$ denotes the sum of the products of frequency and corresponding weights, and N represents the number of respondents. The computed values were interpreted using a five-point Likert scale with descriptive equivalents. For the extent of practice, the scale ranged from Not Practiced to Very Highly Practiced, while for the seriousness of problems, the scale ranged from Not a Problem to Highly Serious. These interpretations served as the basis for proposing intervention measures to address the identified challenges in TVL instruction.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the data gathered and their analysis and interpretation to answer the sub-problems raised in the study.

Extent of Practice of Teaching Strategies of Technology-Vocational-Livelihood Teachers

This section presents the extent of practices of teaching strategies of Technology-Vocational-Livelihood (TVL) teachers in terms of entrepreneurial, contextualized, experiential, constructivist and authentic teaching strategies to answer sub-problem number 1.

The data are presented in Tables 1A, 1B, 1C, 1D, and 1E.

Entrepreneurial Teaching Strategies

Table 1A
Extent of Practice of TVL Teachers of Entrepreneurial Strategies

INDICATORS	WM	DE
● Introduce the students on business concept to develop their business sense and open their mind on business opportunities.	4.37	HP
● Equip the students with knowledge on solving business problems and turned problems into opportunities.	4.26	HP
● Develop the students' self-confidence and resiliency	4.43	HP

to prepare them on facing problems, risks and failure.		
● Inculcate the spirit of hard work to the students to lead them to give their best shot on every endeavors, projects and products.	4.38	HP
● Provide the students with basic knowledge on costing, pricing, purchasing, profiting, and resourcing of materials and/or ingredients to prepare them for a business opportunity.	4.42	HP
● Develop their skills on baking/masonry/electrical/electronics to uplift their confidence on their work output.	4.27	HP
● Inspire the students to be creative to maximize available materials and be able to find ways on resolving missing ingredients and/or absence of materials.	4.35	HP
● Develop students' understanding on Technology Vocational Livelihood concepts.	4.42	HP
● Motivate students to explore business opportunities based on their TVL learning.	4.37	HP
● Prepare students on the actual world of business by providing them real training exercises.	4.31	HP
Overall WM	4.36	HP
Legend: WM=Weighted Mean		
Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)
5	4.50-5.00	Very Highly Practiced (VHP)
4	3.50-4.49	Highly Practiced (HP)
3	2.50-3.49	Moderately Practiced (MP)
2	1.50-2.49	Less Practiced (LP)
1	1.00-1.49	Not Practiced (NP)

As presented in Table 1A, the extent of practice of the entrepreneurial teaching strategy showed that the indicator “Develop the students’ self-confidence and resiliency to prepare them in facing problems, risks, and even failure” obtained the highest weighted mean of 4.43, while the indicator “Equip the students with knowledge in solving business problems and turn problems into opportunities” received the lowest weighted mean of 4.26. Despite the difference in ratings, both indicators were interpreted as highly practiced. The overall weighted mean of 4.36 further indicates that entrepreneurial teaching strategies are highly practiced by the respondents. These findings suggest that the implementation of entrepreneurial teaching strategies helps create a dynamic and engaging learning environment that nurtures students’ entrepreneurial mindset, enhances their problem-

solving abilities, and prepares them to become resilient individuals capable of responding to challenges in the ever-evolving global economy.

Contextualized Teaching Strategies

Table 1B
Extent of Practice of TVL Teachers of Contextualized Strategies

INDICATORS	WM	DE
● Consider the students with different ethnic origin to serve as a source of first-hand information on the topic related to their culture.	3.95	HP
● Consider students' diversity in bringing their different point of view and varied approaches to the learning process.	4.05	HP
● Encourage students to share their personal experiences and background to interact and collaborate with their classmates during the group activity.	4.34	HP
● Motivate learners to perform independently about proper maintenance of electrical tools and equipment, kitchen wares and utensils, computer accessories, and the like.	4.31	HP
● Students are asked to internalize the health and safety procedures through safety measures.	4.41	HP
● Require the students to prepare a sketch and layout of their own kitchen at home, electrical wiring diagram or computer specifications design.	3.94	HP
● Teach students to use appropriate tools, utensils and the like for the job required.	4.33	HP
● Teach students to perform correct methods of calculations to get accuracy on measurement.	4.29	HP
● Perform correct methods of calculations to get accuracy of measurement.	4.32	HP
● Take into account students' prior knowledge when planning class program for TVL lessons.	4.21	HP
Overall WM	4.36	HP
Legend: WM=Weighted Mean		

Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)
5	4.50-5.00	Very Highly Practiced (VHP)
4	3.50-4.49	Highly Practiced (HP)
3	2.50-3.49	Moderately Practiced (MP)
2	1.50-2.49	Less Practiced (LP)
1	1.00-1.49	Not Practiced (NP)

As presented in Table 1B, all indicators on the extent of practice of TVL teachers along contextualized teaching strategies were interpreted as highly practiced, with weighted means ranging from 3.94 to 4.41. The highest rating was obtained by the indicator “Learners were asked to internalize the health and safety procedures through safety measures” with a weighted mean of 4.41, while the lowest rating was “Require the students to prepare a sketch and layout of their own kitchen at home, electrical wiring diagram, or computer specifications design” with a weighted mean of 3.94. The overall weighted mean of 4.22 indicates that contextualized teaching strategies are highly practiced by the respondents. These findings suggest that teachers frequently connect lessons to real-life situations and practical experiences, enabling learners to better understand and apply concepts. Through contextualization, abstract knowledge is linked to authentic situations, making learning more meaningful, engaging, and relevant to students’ everyday lives.

Experiential Teaching Strategies

Table 1C
Extent of Practice of TVL Teachers of Experiential Strategies

INDICATORS	WM	DE
● Let the students learn by doing mostly in workplace like kitchen laboratory, welding/electronic facilities and/or computer laboratory.	4.30	HP
● Wear personal protective equipment and consider Japanese 5S Productivity Philosophy.	4.45	HP
● Listen and ask questions to the students to gauge their level of understanding.	4.42	HP
● Utilize video lessons and activities.	4.41	HP
● Expose the class to the use of investigative strategies.	4.28	HP
● Use indigenous materials in teaching TVL.	4.12	HP
● Give students hands-on experience in choosing equipment/tools/utensils appropriately.	4.34	HP
● Develop the students’ motor skills in using scientific, industrial tools or creative media.	4.15	HP

● Enable students to design and create objects or equipment in different physical media.	4.29	HP
● Apply a combination of synchronous tools such as web conferencing, asynchronous tools such as discussion forms and/or social media for group work, e-portfolios and multimedia for reporting and remote labs for experimental works.	4.31	HP
Overall WM	4.31	HP
Legend: WM=Weighted Mean		
Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)
5	4.50-5.00	Very Highly Practiced (VHP)
4	3.50-4.49	Highly Practiced (HP)
3	2.50-3.49	Moderately Practiced (MP)
2	1.50-2.49	Less Practiced (LP)
1	1.00-1.49	Not Practiced (NP)

Table 1C presents the practice of TVL teachers in terms of experiential teaching strategy as assessed by the teachers themselves. The indicator “Wearing personal protective equipment and considering Japanese 5S Productivity Philosophy” obtained the highest weighted mean of 4.45, while the indicator “Use indigenous materials in teaching TVL” received the lowest weighted mean of 4.12. Despite the difference in ratings, both indicators were interpreted as highly practiced. The overall weighted mean of 4.31 further indicates that experiential teaching strategies are highly practiced by the respondents. These findings suggest that teachers frequently engage students in hands-on learning activities that allow them to apply concepts in practical situations. The experiential teaching approach highlights the cyclical process of experiencing, reflecting, and applying new knowledge, which promotes deeper understanding and retention of learning by connecting classroom instruction with real-world experiences.

Constructivist Teaching Strategies

Table 1D
Extent of Practice of TVL Teachers of Constructivist Strategies

INDICATORS	WM	DE
● Motivate the students to create scenarios of their learning experiences by writing reflective journals or creating personal blogs through digital portfolios (cooking books, recipe blogs, food plating videos, demo videos).	4.25	HP
● Provide real world case based on learning environments rather than pre-determined instructional events.	4.18	HP
● Use technology to come up with something new and	4.12	HP

unique through product innovation considering proper nutrition and availability of ingredients or raw materials needed for production.		
● Allow students to work in group.	4.31	HP
● Motivate the students to use instructional tool as a primary source rather than a textbook.	4.29	HP
● Allow the students or the team to do the task entirely on their own, the teachers provide help and assistance as needed.	4.34	HP
● Encourage students to use appropriate local materials as substitute for listed materials that are not available.	4.17	HP
● Diagnose and troubleshoot computer system. Able to diagnose and configure computer system and network. Able to adjust flavors on baking and cooking. Able to detect wiring problems.	4.02	HP
● Encourage students to relate what they have learned in TLE class to their life outside of school.	4.29	HP
● Allow students to work at the speed which suits their ability and adjust depending on the activity needs.	4.16	HP
Overall WM	4.21	HP
Legend: WM=Weighted Mean		
Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)
5	4.50-5.00	Very Highly Practiced (VHP)
4	3.50-4.49	Highly Practiced (HP)
3	2.50-3.49	Moderately Practiced (MP)
2	1.50-2.49	Less Practiced (LP)
1	1.00-1.49	Not Practiced (NP)

Table 1D presents the assessment of teaching strategies of TVL teachers in terms of constructivist teaching strategy. The indicator “Allow the students or the team to do the task entirely on their own; the teachers provide help and assistance as needed” obtained the highest weighted mean of 4.34, while the indicator “Diagnose and troubleshoot computer system; able to diagnose and configure computer system and network; able to adjust flavors in baking and cooking; able to detect wiring problems” received the lowest weighted mean of 4.02. Despite the variation in ratings, both indicators were interpreted as highly practiced. The overall weighted mean of 4.21 further indicates that constructivist teaching strategies are highly practiced by the respondents. These results imply that teachers frequently encourage students to actively participate in learning tasks and develop their skills through independent and collaborative activities. By implementing constructivist teaching strategies, teachers create a dynamic and engaging learning

environment where learners construct their own knowledge, leading to deeper understanding and more meaningful learning experiences.

Authentic Teaching Strategies

Table 1E
Extent of Practice of TVL Teachers of Authentic Strategies

INDICATORS	WM	DE
● Motivate students to focus their tasks on contextualizing rather than abstracting.	4.24	HP
● Allow students to rate their work by comparing their output with the evaluation sample or based on the rubric for scoring.	4.24	HP
● Relate the concept of TVL to other disciplines like Science, Mathematics and Languages.	4.18	HP
● Relate TVL to current technology.	4.41	HP
● Guide students in applying technology in launching business/livelihood program.	4.38	HP
● Allow the use of calculator/computers/LCD projector for drills and practices and to collect and analyze data.	4.19	HP
● Encourage students to practice working if they have the materials/equipment/tools/utensils at home.	4.34	HP
● Develop skills and confidence by encouraging them to present demo presentation.	4.31	HP
● Engage in a role play of a particular TVL activity. Describe what might happen if one element of the activity is missing. Be able to present solution.	4.22	HP
● Develop a business/marketing/sales plan for an imaginary or real company in a student area of interest.	4.35	HP
Overall WM	4.21	HP
Legend: WM=Weighted Mean		
Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)
5	4.50-5.00	Very Highly Practiced (VHP)
4	3.50-4.49	Highly Practiced (HP)
3	2.50-3.49	Moderately Practiced (MP)
2	1.50-2.49	Less Practiced (LP)
1	1.00-1.49	Not Practiced (NP)

Table 1E presents the teaching strategies of TVL teachers as assessed by themselves in terms of authentic teaching strategy. The indicator “Relate TVL to current technology” obtained the highest weighted mean of 4.41, while the indicator “Relate the concept of TVL to other disciplines like Science, Mathematics, and Languages” received the lowest weighted mean of 4.18. Despite the difference in ratings, both indicators were interpreted as highly practiced. The overall weighted mean of 4.29 indicates that authentic teaching strategies are highly practiced by the respondents. These findings imply that teachers frequently integrate real-life applications and contemporary technologies into their instruction. Authentic learning provides learners with opportunities to engage in meaningful real-world tasks and assessments that promote higher-order thinking skills and competencies, while encouraging students to produce useful and practical outputs that can be applied beyond the classroom.

Summary Table

Teaching Strategies	WM	DE
Entrepreneurial	4.36	Highly Practiced
Contextualized	4.22	Highly Practiced
Experiential	4.31	Highly Practiced
Constructivist	4.21	Highly Practiced
Authentic	4.29	Highly Practiced
OVERALL WM	4.28	Highly Practiced

As presented in the Summary Table, entrepreneurial teaching strategy ranked first with an average weighted mean of 4.36, followed by experiential teaching strategy with an average weighted mean of 4.31. Authentic teaching strategy ranked third with an average weighted mean of 4.29, while contextualized teaching strategy placed fourth with an average weighted mean of 4.22. Constructivist teaching strategy ranked last with an average weighted mean of 4.21. All five teaching strategies were described as practiced, with a grand overall weighted mean of 4.28, interpreted as highly practiced. These results indicate that TVL teachers employ various teaching strategies to a great extent in delivering instruction. The findings further suggest that teachers demonstrate mastery and confidence in teaching the subject matter while effectively contextualizing learning plans and instructional strategies based on the curriculum standards prescribed by the Department of Education.

Problems Being Encountered by the Teachers in Teaching Technology-Vocational Livelihood

Table 2
Problems Being Encountered by the Teachers in Teaching Technology-Vocational Livelihood

INDICATORS	WM	DE
● Inadequate facilities and equipment	4.67	HS
● Inadequate teacher training and competency	4.63	HS
● Lack of instructional materials	4.47	VS
● Increased workloads of teachers	4.31	VS
● Student engagement and learning styles	4.22	VS
● Curriculum alignment and assessment	3.95	VS
● Time constraints	3.33	MS
● Crowded classrooms	2.18	SS
● Some students too dependent on teachers	2.12	SS
● Monitoring of students not consistent	1.94	SS
Overall WM	3.58	VS
Legend: WM = Weighted Mean Legend: WM=Weighted Mean		
Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)
5	4.50-5.00	Highly Serious (HS)
4	3.50-4.49	Very Serious (VS)
3	2.50-3.49	Moderately Serious (MS)
2	1.50-2.49	Slightly Serious (SS)
1	1.00-1.49	Not A Problem (NAP)

As presented in Table 2, TVL teachers encounter problems ranging from slightly serious to highly serious in the implementation of the Technology-Vocational-Livelihood (TVL) program. The most critical issues identified were inadequate facilities and equipment and inadequate teacher training and competency, with weighted means of 4.67 and 4.63, respectively. Due to the practical nature of TVL, sufficient tools, equipment, and instructional materials are essential for students to apply their skills and gain meaningful learning experiences. Inadequate facilities and equipment limit opportunities for hands-on practice, while gaps in teacher training and competency hinder the effective delivery of lessons, particularly in specialized areas such as ICT, Industrial Arts, and Agri-Fishery Arts. Teachers may struggle to integrate modern technologies or teaching methods into their lessons, which can affect both the quality of instruction and student learning outcomes.

Other challenges identified as very serious include the lack of instructional materials (WM = 4.47), increased teacher workloads (WM = 4.31), student engagement and learning styles (WM = 4.22), and curriculum alignment and assessment (WM = 3.95). Adequate instructional materials are essential for students to understand lessons and develop skills effectively. Meanwhile, increased workloads due to curriculum changes and evolving instructional expectations can lead to stress, burnout, and reduced teacher performance. Additionally, TVL teachers face challenges in maintaining student engagement and accommodating diverse learning styles during hands-on activities, as well as aligning curriculum, teaching strategies, and assessments within limited class time. Addressing these concerns is vital to ensuring the effectiveness of the TVL program, which equips learners with practical, job-ready skills that can generate economic benefits and enhance their employability.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Generally, the teachers highly practiced different teaching strategies in teaching Technology Vocational Livelihood (TVL) to a great extent which indicates they can teach with mastery and confidence of the subject matter and try to contextualize the learning plan and strategy prescribed in the curriculum materials provided by the Department of Education.
2. Problems being encountered by the teachers in teaching TVL include inadequate facilities and equipment, inadequate teacher training and competency and lack of instructional materials.
3. The proposed intervention measures focused on solutions to address the moderately serious to highly serious problems being encountered by teachers in teaching TVL.

Recommendations

On the basis of the findings and conclusions drawn, the following recommendations were offered:

1. The proposed intervention measures should be considered for implementation to address the problems being encountered by teachers.
2. School administration should conduct more seminars and trainings related to teachers' area of specialization.
3. Teachers should be encouraged to explore other effective teaching strategies to become more global in perspective.
4. School authorities should regularly evaluate the Technology-Vocational-Livelihood program for its improvements/enhancement.
5. There should be more hands-on activities for the students to be supervised by the teachers to fully equip the students for technical-vocational courses.
6. To improve the professionalism of the Technology-Vocational-Livelihood teachers, it is recommended that they upgrade themselves through professional development activities.

7. Similar studies may be conducted on a wider scope to validate the findings of the study.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In the conduct of this study, ethical standards were strictly observed to ensure the protection and respect of the participants. Permission to conduct the research was secured from the school administration prior to data collection. The respondents were informed about the purpose of the study, and their participation was entirely voluntary. Confidentiality and anonymity of the respondents were maintained, and the information gathered was used solely for academic and research purposes. The researcher also ensured that no harm, coercion, or misrepresentation occurred during the data collection process, and all data were handled responsibly and reported with honesty and integrity.

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